

THE STRESS SIMULATION ANALYSIS OF COPPER ALLOY C84400 IN A HELICAL GEAR

Muhammad Roby Subarkah^{1*}, Irsyadi Yani²

¹University of Sriwijaya, roby1495@gmail.com

²University of Sriwijaya,

Author Correspondence: Palembang, Indonesia, Email address

Abstract

The Copper Alloy-Zeng is an alloy of copper and zinc in proportions that can be varied to achieve various mechanical and electrical properties. In a mechanical system, the gears are an important component used to increase or decrease torque, change the direction of motion and transmit power from a motion system. The easy alternative for carrying out calculations and comparing them with real conditions is simulation analysis. The stress analysis uses the finite element method with Solidworks 2021 software to save time and costs. The aim of this research is to analyze Von Misses stress using the finite element method with Solidworks 2021 software on helical gears made from copper alloy type Copper Alloy C84400 to obtain the Von Misses value where the Von Misses value can predict material failure. The result of this research was the Von Misses Stress values in this study are based on different forces, namely 10 N, 20 N, 30 N, 40 N, and 50 N, which have Von Misses Stress values of 0.085 MPa, 0.171 MPa, 0.256 MPa, 0.341 MPa and 0.427 MPa. Because the Von Misses Stress value that occurs is below the yield strength value of 105 MPa, this helical gear only experiences elastic deformation. The results of the analysis of the helical gear at forces of 10 N, 20 N, 30 N, 40 N, and 50 N showed safety factor values of 1230, 615, 410, 308, and 246, indicating that the strength of the material > the stress that occurs. Therefore it can be said that this helical gear is not safe to use.

Keywords: *Copper alloy, Helical Gear, Solidworks 2021, Von misses.*

1. Introduction

In a mechanical system, the gears are an important component used to increase or decrease torque, change the direction of motion and transmit power from a motion system (Martin and Suwandi, 2020). In the design of gears, forming materials with various variations and properties are considered, such as mechanical design requirements, resistance and strength to face defects, in addition to considering the production capacity of gears, preparation of gears, formation of gear teeth, assembly of gears to engine, weight, appearance, corrosion resistance, sound and cost (Sutanto, 2017). There are several types of gears based on their geometric shape, including straight gears, helical gears, conical gears, worm gears and others.

The Copper Alloy-Zeng is an alloy of copper and zinc in proportions that can be varied to achieve various mechanical and electrical properties. Brass is an alloy of 70% copper and 30% zinc. However, the proportions of copper and zinc can be varied to obtain various brasses with varying mechanical properties. Brass has higher malleability and a low melting point (900°C to 940°C) depending on its composition.

There are several types of copper alloys based on the chemical composition contained, one of which is red and leaded brasses with serial numbers C83300 – C85800 with the chemical composition Cu-Zn-Sn-Pb (75-85% Cu). To avoid damage to a tool, a design that is safe enough is needed, so an analysis is carried out to determine the value of the Von Misses stress of the material. The Von Misses stress is an accurate prediction of the failure of ductile materials that experience static forceing, pure alternating forceing, shear forceing or combined forceing (Walidina, et al., 2022).The easy alternative for carrying out calculations and comparing them with real conditions is simulation analysis.

The use of simulation analysis has been widely used in various applications. To save time and costs, computer simulations are often used in industries that continue to move quickly. The stress analysis uses the finite element method with Solidworks 2021 software. The finite element method is a numerical mathematical technique for calculating the structural strength of engineering components by dividing objects into mesh shapes.

The one type of material in helical gears is Copper Alloy Series C84400 which is commonly used in water valves, pumps, pipe fittings and piping accessories (Copper Development Association Inc.). This helical gearwith Copper Alloy C84400 material is one part of the reciprocating pump which is usually used to pump chemical solutions at PT.P.

This helical gear often gets damaged which can affect production performance during use. Improper analysis of process parameters such as volume-based percentages of copper and zinc, pressure and their interactions in the manufacture of copper-zinc alloys has created great challenges in the manufacture of alloys (Olodu and Okagbare, 2021).

The aim of this research is to analyze Von Misses stress using the finite element method with Solidworks 2021 software on helical gears made from copper alloy type Copper Alloy C84400 to obtain the Von Misses value where the Von Misses value can predict material failure. The results of this analysis can be a consideration in selecting the right materials to maximize the function of the tool so that it can work optimally.

2. The Research Methodology

In this research, the analysis used Solid works 2021 software. This research was carried out based on the procedure shown in the figure:

2.1 The Modeling

In the initial stages of modeling, direct measurements of the helical gear must be carried out. The data obtained is as follows:

Table 1 : The measuring results of helical gear specification

No	Size	Symbol	Unit	Value
1	Power	P	hp	1
2	Speed	Np	rpm	1425
3	Motor Torque	t	Nm	4.984
4	Gear Diameter	D	mm	212
5	Gear Width	B	mm	70
6	Modulus	M	mm	4
7	Number of Gear	Z	-	51
8	Helic Angle	ψ	derajat	30

The results of the measurements above show the specifications of the electric motor used to drive the pump, from which we can find out the torque of the electric motor used.

Figure 1. Tilt gear in Solid works 2021 Software

2.2 The Additional Materials

After carrying out 3D modeling in Solidworks 2021 software, before proceeding to the next procedure, we must add materials to the 3D design that we have created. The material used in this simulation is Copper Alloy C84400 material with the following mechanical properties:

Tensile Strength : 235 Mpa
Yield Strength : 105 Mpa
Elastic modulus : 90 GPa (13.0 x 10⁶ psi)
Density : 9.70 g/cm³

2.3 The Boundary and forcing Conditions

The boundary conditions for this helical gear are at the fulcrum point as follows:

Figure 2. The locking fulcrum point

Figure 3. The fulcrum point on the inside of the gear

Figure 4. The forcing area and direction

2.4 The Element Distribution

At this stage, the elements or meshing of the gears are divided to analyze the statics of the helical gears.

Figure 5. The element distribution or Meshing

2.5 The Running Simulation

At this stage, the calculations and analysis are carried out by Solidworks 2021 software on the forces, materials and other parameters that have been given.

3. Results

3.1 Von Misses Stress

The results of this simulation can be seen that the gears experience a maximum stress of 0.085 MPa with a force of 10 N in the area shown in the analysis image below.

Figure 6. Von misses stress at a force of 10 N

Then in the simulation a force of 20 N given to the helical gear produces a maximum stress of 0.171 Mpa and can be seen in the picture below.

Figure 7. Von misses stress at a force of 20 N

In the simulation, a force of 30 N given to the helical gear produces a maximum stress of 0.256 Mpa and can be seen in the picture below.

Figure 8. Von misses stress at a force of 30 N

In the simulation, a force of 40 N given to the helical gear produces a maximum stress of 0.341 Mpa and can be seen in the picture below.

Figure 9. Von misses stress at a force of 40 N

In the simulation, a force of 50 N given to the helical gear produces a maximum stress of 0.427 Mpa and can be seen in the picture below.

Figure 10. Von misses stress at a force of 50 N

The overall results can be seen in the table below:

Table 2. The Von Misses stress simulation results

No	The force (N)	Yield Strength (MPa)	Von Misses Value (MPa)
1	10	105	0.085
2	20	105	0.171
3	30	105	0.256
4	40	105	0.341
5	50	105	0.427

3.2 Factor of Safety

From the 10 N force simulation, the safety factor results for the helical gear obtained a minimum value of 1230, and the maximum result was 61,75,648.

Figure 11. Factor of safety at a force of 10 N

From the 20 N force simulation, the safety factor results for the helical gear obtained a minimum value of 615, and the maximum result was 30,887,824.

Figure 12. Factor of safety at a force of 20 N

From the 30 N force simulation, the safety factor results for the helical gears obtained a minimum value of 410, and the maximum result was 20,591,874.

Figure 13. Factor of safety at a force of 30 N

From the 40 N force simulation, the safety factor results for the helical gear obtained a minimum value of 308, and the maximum result was 15,443,912.

Figure 14. Factor of safety at a force of 40 N

From the 50 N force simulation, the safety factor results for the helical gears obtained a minimum value of 246, and the maximum result was 12,355,128.

Figure 15. Factor of safety at a force of 50 N

The overall results of the Factor of Safety values can be seen in the table below:

Table 3. The factor of safety simulation results

No	The force (N)	Yield Limit (MPa)	Factor Of Safety minimum	Factor Of Safety maximum
1	10	105	1230	61.75.648
2	20	105	615	30.887.824
3	30	105	410	20.591.874
4	40	105	308	15433192
5	50	105	246	12355128

4. Discussion

In this research, simulations have been carried out on helical gears to obtain Von Misses Stress values. Von Misses Stress determines the maximum stress value in static or immovable conditions and differentiates it from the yield strength of the material used. Von Misses stress can predict the failure of ductile materials that experience static forcing, pure alternating forcing, shear forcing or combined forcing. In this research, the helical gear material used is Cooper alloy C84400 which has material yield strength of 105 MPa with a chemical composition of Cu-Zn-Sn-Pb (75-85% Cu).

The choice of helical gear shape is determined based on the utility value of the tool which is commonly used in water valves, pumps, pipe fittings and piping accessories. One of the uses of the helical gear at PT.P is as a component in the chemical solution pump. From the results of static analysis on helical gears made of Copper Alloy C84400 using Solidworks 2021 software, the Von Misses Stress value at a force of 10 N is 0.085 MPa, 20 N is 0.171 MPa, 30 N is 0.256 MPa, 40 N is 0.341, and 50 N is 0.427 MPa.

The Copper Alloy C84400 material can be said to be safe because the maximum stress figure is below the yield strength figure based on the yield strength figure. From the analysis of the helical gear factor of safety (FOS), at a force of 10 N the minimum result ,was 1230 and the maximum was 61,75,648, at a force of 20 N the minimum result was 615 and the maximum was 30,887,824, at a force of 30 N the minimum result was 410 and the maximum was 20,591.874, a force of 40 N obtained a minimum result of 308 and a maximum of 15,433,192, and a force of 50 N obtained a minimum result of 246 and a maximum result of 12,355,128. The Factor of Safety value in the helical gear simulation with Copper Alloy C84400 material does not meet the safety factor value of 1.25 to 2 because it gets a value above it.

5. Conclusion

Based on the results of the research and simulations that have been carried out, the following conclusions can be obtained:

1. The Von Misses Stress values in this study are based on different forces, namely 10 N, 20 N, 30 N, 40 N, and 50 N, which have Von Misses Stress values of 0.085 MPa, 0.171 MPa, 0.256 MPa, 0.341 MPa and 0.427 MPa. Because the Von Misses Stress value that occurs is below the yield strength value of 105 MPa, this helical gear only experiences elastic deformation.
2. The results of the analysis of the helical gear at forces of 10 N, 20 N, 30 N, 40 N, and 50 N showed safety factor values of 1230, 615, 410, 308, and 246, indicating that the strength of the material > the stress that occurs. Therefore it can be said that this helical gear is not safe to use.

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